

EXACT SOLUTIONS OF THE ISING MODELS IN A MAGNETIC FIELD

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Abstract

Previously, the author solved the one-, two- and three-dimensional Ising models in the absence of an external magnetic field exactly. Additional convincing proofs for these solutions are given here. The exact solutions of the Ising models in a magnetic field are found. It is shown that the conventional methods of solving the Ising models are incorrect. Heat capacities and zero-field magnetic susceptibilities of the Ising models are calculated exactly for all dimensions (including the case of polonium) and a flaw in Onsager's solution for heat capacity is detected. (It is shown that Onsager's solution of the two-dimensional Ising model is wrong).

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1. Introduction

The exact solutions of the one-, two- and three-dimensional Ising models in the absence of a magnetic field were obtained previously [1]. They were derived using the correlation function. Other strong proofs (including one with a numerical experiment) of the correctness of these solutions are given in this study. The next step is to obtain the exact solutions of the Ising models in the presence of an external magnetic field, which is achieved in this work. It is shown that the traditional approach to the solutions of the Ising models based on the differentiation of the partition function with respect to a magnetic field is false. Using the theory developed by the author, we can calculate exactly heat capacities and zero-field magnetic susceptibilities for the Ising model in all dimensions. The heat capacity of polonium is calculated in the frame of the three-dimensional Ising model. A discrepancy between Onsager's solutions for heat capacity and magnetisation is also found because Onsager's solution of the two-dimensional Ising model is wrong.

2. Theory

2.1. Solution of the one-dimensional Ising model

An exact solution of the one-dimensional Ising model in the absence of a magnetic field was obtained previously by the author [1]. Let us present an improved version of this solution here. Let us consider the one-dimensional Ising model in the absence of an external magnetic field [2]: the Hamiltonian of a chain of N atoms is of the form:

$$\mathcal{H} = - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} J_i s_i s_{i+1}, \quad (1)$$

where the spins s_i are one-dimensional unit vectors assuming only the discrete values $+1$ and -1 , and J_i is the interaction energy between spins situated on sites i and $i + 1$. Positive and negative J_i values favour parallel

and antiparallel alignments of the spins, respectively. The partition function of this chain is:

$$Z_N = \sum_{s_1=-1}^1 \sum_{s_2=-1}^1 \cdots \sum_{s_N=-1}^1 \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \beta J_i s_i s_{i+1}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $\beta = \frac{1}{kT}$.

For a chain of two spins, the Hamiltonian will be:

$$\mathcal{H} = -J_1 s_1 s_2. \quad (3)$$

The partition function of this chain is:

$$Z_2 = \sum_{s_1=-1}^1 \sum_{s_2=-1}^1 \exp(\beta J_1 s_1 s_2) = 4 \cosh(\beta J_1). \quad (4)$$

Now, we can calculate the nearest-neighbour correlation function for a chain of two spins:

$$\Gamma_1(1) \equiv \langle s_1 s_2 \rangle = Z_2^{-1} \sum_{\{s\}} s_1 s_2 \exp(\beta J_1 s_1 s_2) = \tanh(\beta J_1). \quad (5)$$

In $\Gamma_1(1)$, the subscript denotes that the correlation function is of the spin 1, in brackets is the distance between spins, in units of a lattice constant, and the summation is over spins s_1 and s_2 . In [2], with the exact calculation, it was shown that for a chain of N spins:

$$\Gamma_k(1) = \tanh(\beta J_k), \quad (6)$$

where $\Gamma_k(1)$ is the k th spin correlation function. It is important to notice that this expression does not depend on the number of spins in the chain [1] and is identical to that in equation (5).

In [2], the long-range correlation function for a chain of N spins was calculated:

$$\Gamma_k(r) \equiv \langle s_k s_{k+r} \rangle = Z_N^{-1} \sum_{\{s\}} s_k s_{k+r} \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \beta J_i s_i s_{i+1}\right), \quad (7)$$

where the symbol $\{s\}$ denotes the N -fold summation of equation (2). Here, r is the distance between spins, in units of a lattice constant. This function equals:

$$\Gamma_k(r) = \tanh(\beta J_k) \tanh(\beta J_{k+1}) \cdots \tanh(\beta J_{k+r-1}) = \prod_{i=1}^r \tanh(\beta J_{k+i-1}). \quad (8)$$

Now, it is possible to find the temperature at which long-range order sets in, namely the temperature at which the two-spin correlation function declines sufficiently slowly with the interspin distance that the chain becomes magnetic. The squared normalised zero-field magnetisation is [2]:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{M(T, H = 0)^2}{M(T = 0, H = 0)^2} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \Gamma_k(r), \quad (9)$$

where H is the external magnetic field. From equation (8), we can see that the hyperbolic tangents are less than one and hence the products approach zero in the limit of infinite r . The linear chain, therefore, displays zero spontaneous magnetisation for all non-zero values of the temperature.

Nevertheless, there is a mistake in the proof given by equations (8) and (9). Consider a uniform chain consisting of 1000 spins, $J_k = J$ for all k and $\Gamma(1) = 0.999$ (subscript is omitted for simplicity). Its squared magnetisation from equations (8) and (9) is [1] $\sigma^2 \approx 0.37$. Now, let us assume that $J_{500} = 0$. Then, from equations (8) and (9), $\sigma^2 = 0$. This is an incorrect result. In reality, the chain will split into two chains with $\sigma^2 \approx 0.61$ each. This proves that the solution of the one-dimensional model provided in [2] is invalid.

There is another flaw in the proof given by equations (8) and (9). Let us assume theoretically that the correct solution of the one-dimensional Ising

model exists and, according to it, in the chain 90% of the spins are up and 10% are down. Then, equations (8) and (9) predict that the magnetisation of this chain is zero. Therefore, this proof is not able to detect magnetisation.

Consider a uniform infinite Ising chain with a strong correlation, for example, $\Gamma(1) = 0.999$. This means that the two cases are possible. The first one is: a chain with $\sim 99.9\%$ of the spins turned up and $\sim 0.1\%$ of them turned down. Such a chain will possess magnetisation according to the definition of the correlation function. From equation (9), it follows that for the uniform chain the magnetisation is:

$$\sigma^2 = \Gamma(1). \quad (10)$$

A rigorous proof of equation (10) for large N is given in the Appendix.

The second case is for a chain consisting of domains, with each one having on average 2000 spins (for an infinite chain). In some of the domains, the spins are turned up and in the others they are turned down. The net magnetisation is zero. This is called domain magnetism. In [3], it was argued that the first case takes place and that the second case is less likely because of physical reasons.

Therefore, the one-dimensional Ising model has two solutions. The magnetisation of a uniform Ising chain is defined by one elementary cell. The elementary cell consists of a spin and its nearest neighbour. The first solution results in magnetisation that is equal to that of one elementary cell. From equation (10), it follows that this normalised zero-field magnetisation is:

$$\sigma = \Gamma(1)^{0.5} = \tanh(\beta J)^{0.5}. \quad (11)$$

The plot of this magnetisation is given in Figure 1. The magnetisation decreases from unity at $T = 0$ and asymptotically tends to zero with temperature. The second solution predicts domain magnetism with zero total magnetisation. Furthermore, in this study, the first solution will be considered because it is physically more interesting. The magnetisation of a

non-uniform Ising chain will be equal to that of an average elementary cell:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \tanh(\beta J_i)}{N-1}. \quad (12)$$

Other authors use another solution of the one-dimensional Ising model [4-10]. They use the equation:

$$M(T, H) = kT \left. \frac{\partial \ln Z_N}{\partial H} \right|_{H=0}, \quad (13)$$

where in the partition function Z_N they sum over all possible configurations with N_1 spins up and $N - N_1$ spins down, where N_1 changes from 0 to N . However, if $\Gamma(1) = 0.999$, in Case 1 described above, the number $N - N_1$ is $\sim 0.1\%$ of N and configurations with $N - N_1$ not equal to 0.1% are impossible and may not be taken into account. In addition, from equations (2) and (4), it follows that the partition function Z_N of a uniform Ising chain is:

$$Z_N = 4^{N-1} \cosh(\beta J)^{N-1} = Z_2^{N-1}, \quad (14)$$

which differs very much from the partition functions obtained in [4-10].

Let us check equation (13). The Hamiltonian of a uniform chain in magnetic field is [4, 5, 9, 10]:

$$\mathcal{H} = - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} J s_i s_{i+1} - H \sum_{i=1}^N s_i, \quad (15)$$

where H is the magnetic field in energy units. This Hamiltonian will be the sum of the Hamiltonians of the elementary cells:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 + \mathcal{H}_2 + \mathcal{H}_3 + \dots, \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathcal{H}_i = -J s_i s_{i+1} - \frac{H s_i}{2} - \frac{H s_{i+1}}{2} \quad (17)$$

for $i \neq 1$ and $i \neq N - 1$. Here, the factors $1/2$ mean that the spins belong to this cell and to the neighbour cells. A cell described by equation (17) produces, in line with equation (13), zero magnetisation for $H = 0$:

$$\sigma = \frac{\exp(\beta J) \sinh(\beta H)}{\exp(\beta J) \cosh(\beta H) + \exp(-\beta J)}. \quad (18)$$

This cannot be true because when $\Gamma(1) = 0.99$, then $\sim 99\%$ of the two-spin Ising chains have parallel spins, thus, there is a magnetisation. We can easily see that for the general Hamiltonian, equation (16), the magnetisation is also zero. This contradicts equation (10).

In [9], equation (13) was applied to a two-dimensional Ising lattice and it was found that:

$$M(T, 0) \sim \frac{\sum_{\{s\}} \left[\sum_{ik} s_{ik} \right] \exp(-\beta \mathcal{H})}{Z_N}, \quad (19)$$

where s_{ik} are the spins of this lattice. Using the Hamiltonians for two-dimensional lattices given in this study, we can show analogously to the one-dimensional chain that in the zero external field, equation (19) results in zero magnetisation. This is the average magnetisation of an array of uncorrelated spins. Therefore, equation (13) is incorrect. We should note here that in [9], equation (13) was used in the derivation of equation (9) of this study. Thus, that derivation is not reliable.

If we know $\Gamma(1)$, we can calculate the number of spins up and down in the chain. In the calculation of the partition function, only the configurations with this number of spins up and down must be taken. Such a partition function will be exact and calculations with it will produce the correct results. Other configurations are impossible and may not be taken into account.

From equation (17), it follows that the magnetisation of the one-dimensional Ising chain in a magnetic field is:

$$\sigma^2(H) = \frac{\cosh(\beta H) - \exp(-2\beta J)}{\cosh(\beta H) + \exp(-2\beta J)}. \quad (20)$$

The partition function for this case is equal to the denominator of equation (20) multiplied by $2 \exp(\beta J)$.

2.2. Solutions of the two- and three-dimensional Ising models

The two- and three-dimensional Ising models in the absence of a magnetic field were solved exactly previously by the author [1]. In [1], it was shown that other solutions of these models were incorrect. Let us present extended versions of these solutions here. In [2, 4, 5, 7-13], solutions of the two- and three-dimensional Ising models were given. They also used equation (13) and sum over all configurations [1], and, therefore, are incorrect. In [14], further evidence was given that the traditional solution of the two-dimensional Ising model is erroneous. For example, the ‘exact solution’ for a square lattice is [5]:

$$\sigma = (1 + u)^{1/4}(1 - u)^{-1/2}(1 - 6u + u^2)^{1/8}, \quad (21)$$

where $u = \exp(-4\beta J)$. For $J = 0$, the magnetisation must be zero, but from equation (21), it follows that the numerator is complex and the denominator is zero.

If we denote the magnetisation of an elementary cell of a crystal lattice by M_i , then the average magnetisation of the two- and three-dimensional Ising lattices is:

$$M = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{cells}}} M_i}{N_{\text{cells}}}, \quad (22)$$

where N_{cells} is the number of elementary cells. If the cells are identical, the normalised magnetisation is equal to that of one elementary cell and can be

written as:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \Gamma_k(1)}{n}, \quad (23)$$

where n is the number of the nearest-neighbour interactions in the cell. In the uniform lattice of equal J , in equation (23), $\sigma^2 = \Gamma(1)$. To calculate $\Gamma(1)$, we must find the partition function of the elementary cell.

The energy of the hexagonal lattice is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H} &= E_1 + E_2 + E_3 + \dots \\ &= \frac{-Js_1s_2 - Js_2s_3 - Js_3s_1}{2} + \frac{-Js_1s_3 - Js_3s_4 - Js_4s_1}{2} + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Here, the first term on the right-hand side is the energy of the first elementary cell, the second term is the energy of the adjacent cell and so on. The Hamiltonian of one cell in a lattice differs from that of a single triangle by division by 2 because every term in the numerator is taken twice (Js_3s_1 and Js_1s_3) in equation (24). For the square lattice, the situation is the same, but, for the simple cubic lattice, it differs from that of a single cube by division by 4.

The partition function of a crystal lattice is:

$$Z = \sum_{\{s\}} \exp[-\beta(E_1 + E_2 + E_3 + \dots)] = Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 \dots, \quad (25)$$

where Z_1, Z_2, Z_3, \dots are the partition functions of the elementary cells. Note that this result is similar to that in equation (14). The partition function of a cell in the hexagonal lattice is:

$$Z_i = 2 \exp(3\beta J/2) + 6 \exp(-\beta J/2). \quad (26)$$

Now, let us find the nearest-neighbour correlation function between the two spins, $\Gamma(1)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma(1) &= \frac{\sum_{\{s\}} s_1 s_2 \exp[-\beta(E_1 + E_2 + E_3 + \dots)]}{Z} \\
&= \frac{\sum_{\{s\}} s_1 s_2 \exp(-\beta E_1) \sum_{\{s\}} \exp(-\beta E_2) \sum_{\{s\}} \exp(-\beta E_3) \dots}{Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 \dots} \\
&= \frac{\sum_{\{s\}} s_1 s_2 \exp(-\beta E_1)}{Z_1}, \tag{27}
\end{aligned}$$

where E_1, E_2, E_3, \dots are defined in equation (24). Thus, this correlation function and the magnetisation are:

$$\Gamma(1) = \sigma^2 = \frac{\exp(2\beta J) - 1}{\exp(2\beta J) + 3}. \tag{28}$$

The plot of the magnetisation is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dependence of the spontaneous magnetisation per spin σ on temperature T for the one-dimensional Ising model, equation (11), (dotted curve), the two-dimensional hexagonal lattice Ising model, equation (28), (solid line) and the two-dimensional square lattice Ising model, equation (31), (dashed line), where $J/k = 1\text{K}$.

In a magnetic field, the term $-H(s_1 + s_2 + s_3)/6$ should be added to the Hamiltonian and the magnetisation becomes:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\exp(2\beta J) \cosh(\beta H/2) - \cosh(\beta H/6)}{\exp(2\beta J) \cosh(\beta H/2) + 3 \cosh(\beta H/6)}. \quad (29)$$

The partition function of this case can be obtained by multiplication of the denominator by $2 \exp(-\beta J/2)$.

Analogously, we can show that the partition function of a cell in a uniform square lattice is:

$$Z_i = 4 \cosh(2\beta J) + 12 \quad (30)$$

and the nearest-neighbour correlation function and magnetisation are:

$$\Gamma(1) = \sigma^2 = \frac{\sinh(2\beta J)}{\cosh(2\beta J) + 3}. \quad (31)$$

The plot of this magnetisation is shown in Figure 1 and it practically coincides with that of equation (28). The magnetisations decrease asymptotically to zero with the temperature from the maximum value at $T = 0$. In a magnetic field, the term $-H(s_1 + s_2 + s_3 + s_4)/4$ must be added to the Hamiltonian and the magnetisation of the square lattice will be:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\exp(2\beta J) \cosh(\beta H) - \exp(-2\beta J)}{\exp(2\beta J) \cosh(\beta H) + \exp(-2\beta J) + 4 \cosh(\beta H/2) + 2}. \quad (32)$$

The partition function of this case is equal to the denominator multiplied by 2.

Using the method developed in [2] (equations (8) and (9) of this study), we can easily show that the long-range correlation function of a two-dimensional lattice is $\Gamma(r) = \Gamma(1)^r$. It tends to zero with r and, therefore, according to [2], this lattice possesses no spontaneous magnetisation. This result contradicts the traditional solution for the two-dimensional model and is additional evidence that the proof proposed in [2] is untenable.

Now, it is possible to find the partition function of a cell in a uniform simple cubic lattice. The Hamiltonian of a cell is:

$$\mathcal{H} = -\frac{J}{4} \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 s_i s_{i+1} + s_4 s_1 + \sum_{i=5}^7 s_i s_{i+1} + s_8 s_5 + \sum_{i=1}^4 s_i s_{i+4} \right) - \frac{H}{8} \sum_{i=1}^8 s_i, \quad (33)$$

and its magnetisation is:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sinh(3\beta J) + 4 \sinh(3\beta J/2) + 5 \sinh(\beta J) + 4 \sinh(\beta J/2)}{\cosh(3\beta J) + 8 \cosh(3\beta J/2) + 15 \cosh(\beta J) + 24 \cosh(\beta J/2) + 16}. \quad (34)$$

The partition function of a cell is equal to the denominator multiplied by 4. The plot of this result is shown in Figure 2. In the presence of a magnetic field, the magnetisation will be $\sigma^2 = A/B$, where

$$\begin{aligned} A = & \exp(3\beta J) \cosh(\beta H) + 4 \exp(3\beta J/2) \cosh(3\beta H/4) \\ & + 4 \exp(\beta J) \cosh(\beta H/2) + 8 \sinh(\beta J/2) \cosh(\beta H/4) \\ & - 4 \exp(-3\beta J/2) \cosh(\beta H/4) + 2 \sinh(\beta J) - 4 \exp(-\beta J) \\ & - \exp(-3\beta J) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} B = & \exp(3\beta J) \cosh(\beta H) + 8 \exp(3\beta J/2) \cosh(3\beta H/4) \\ & + 12 \exp(\beta J) \cosh(\beta H/2) + 48 \cosh(\beta J/2) \cosh(\beta H/4) \\ & + 16 \cosh(\beta H/2) + 8 \exp(-3\beta J/2) \cosh(\beta H/4) + 6 \cosh(\beta J) \\ & + 12 \exp(-\beta J) + \exp(-3\beta J) + 16. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The partition function is equal to $2B$.

2.3. Calculation of heat capacities

Using the theory developed in this study, we can calculate the heat capacities of the one-, two- and three-dimensional Ising models. Some

calculations for the 3-dimensional Ising model were performed already in [15] (in [15], there is a misprint, where in Figure 2, it should read $J/k = 2.4\text{K}$). The isochoric heat capacity of a cell in a crystal lattice can be found from:

$$C_V = k\beta^2 \partial^2 \ln Z_1 / \partial \beta^2, \quad (37)$$

where Z_1 is the partition function of one cell. Its dependence on the temperature is given in Figure 3. In a one-dimensional, quadratic and simple cubic cell, there is one atom in a cell and in a hexagonal cell, there is 0.5 atom. The curve for the three-dimensional model is similar to that of experimental Ising lattices [16] (however, in [16] and the references therein, the transition from paramagnetism to antiferromagnetism was considered). An advantage of the present approach is that the specific heat capacity does not depend on the lattice size, contrary to the results of the previous theories [11, 15, 16]. For an experimental Ising model $0.15 < \beta J < 0.60$ [16], thus, $J/k = 1$ is a reasonable assumption. The square under the curves in Figure 3 is proportional to the heat of the magnetic phase transition. It is equal to 0.877, 1.876, 2.803 and 2.907K for a chain, quadratic, hexagonal and simple cubic lattice, respectively. We can notice a significant value for the hexagonal structure. Here, an analogy with mechanics is evident: a triangle is a stiff figure compared to a rectangle.

In [17], the traditional exact solution for the heat capacity of the 2-dimensional Ising model was made. The dependence of this heat capacity on the temperature was plotted there. It is qualitatively similar to that in Figure 3. It is approximately symmetric regarding the temperature of the phase transition, T_c , which can be found from equation (21): $J/kT_c \approx 0.441$. From equation (21), it follows that at $T > T_c$, there is no magnetisation, and the magnetisation starts to appear only at T_c .

Figure 2. Dependence of spontaneous magnetisation per spin σ on temperature T for the three-dimensional Ising model of the simple cubic lattice, equation (34), where $J/k = 1\text{K}$.

Figure 3. Isochoric heat capacity per atom C_V/k of the Ising lattices versus temperature, equation (37), where $J/k = 1$. From bottom to top (peak heights): one-dimensional chain; square lattice; hexagonal lattice; and simple cubic lattice.

However, according to the plot of heat capacity versus temperature, the magnetisation starts at a much larger temperature than T_c , since when the temperature declines from $T \gg T_c$ to T_c , approximately half of the heat of the phase transition is expressed. This means that around half of the ‘down’ spins turned and became ‘up’ spins. Thus, the solution given in [17] is untenable.

We can try to calculate the heat capacity of polonium at room temperature with equation (37). Polonium is the only element with the simple cubic structure. For polonium, the heat of fusion is $\Delta H = 12.5 \text{ kJ/mol}$ [18], the coordination number is $z = 6$ and the heat capacity is $26.4 \text{ kJ/(mol}\cdot\text{K)}$ [19]. We can obtain the energy J with the formula $2\Delta H/zN$. With this J , equation (37) produces at $T = 298 \text{ K}$ the heat capacity $29.8 \text{ kJ/(mol}\cdot\text{K)}$. For one-dimensional, quadratic and hexagonal structures, the heat capacities of polonium are 3.0, 13.7 and $16.0 \text{ kJ/(mol}\cdot\text{K)}$, respectively.

2.4. Calculation of magnetic susceptibilities

We can calculate the zero-field magnetic susceptibilities for all Ising lattice types:

$$\chi = \left. \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial H} \right|_{H=0}. \quad (38)$$

For a one-dimensional chain, using equation (20), we obtain the following expression:

$$\chi \sim \frac{\beta \sinh(\beta H) \exp(-2\beta J)}{\sigma}. \quad (39)$$

It follows that if a chain possesses a zero-field magnetisation, then χ is zero. If the magnetisation σ of a chain is zero due to domain magnetism, equation (39) cannot be used. We can easily show that the results for the hexagonal, square and simple cubic lattices are the same, the zero-field susceptibility is zero if they have a zero-field magnetisation. In the case of the domain magnetism with zero magnetisation, the problem still requires a solution.

3. Conclusions

Additional strong proofs are found that show that the exact solutions of the 1-, 2- and 3-dimensional Ising models obtained in [1] are correct and their traditional solutions are incorrect. The Ising problem has two solutions. The first one produces spontaneous magnetisation and the second one produces domain magnetism with zero total magnetisation. It is proven (also by numerical simulation) that in the Ising systems the long-range order equals the short-range one, hence, it is enough to calculate the latter one to find the entire magnetisation. Previously, magnetisation was calculated taking the derivative of the partition function with respect to the magnetic field. It is proven that this formula does not produce the magnetisation for the Ising model. Solutions of the Ising models in the presence of an external magnetic field are obtained for all three dimensions. Heat capacities for all dimensions of the Ising model are calculated (including that of polonium) and it is shown that Onsager's 'exact' derivations of the heat capacity and magnetisation for the two-dimensional Ising model contradict each other; and therefore, there is a flaw within them. Zero-field magnetic susceptibilities are also obtained for all dimensions. They are equal to zero if the Ising lattice possesses a zero-field magnetisation, and still need to be solved if the lattice has domain magnetism with zero magnetisation. An attempt to solve the 1-, 2- and 3-dimensional Ising models was made in [22]. The author supposed that magnetisation of the Ising models is that of the elementary cell, but determined the elementary cell of the Ising models differently. The result differs drastically from that obtained in the present study what should be expected.

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Appendix

Derivation of Equation (10)

A general definition of the nearest-neighbour correlation function is the following one:

$$\Gamma(1) = \langle s_i s_{i+1} \rangle - \bar{s}_i \bar{s}_{i+1}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where the last term on the right is the product of uncorrelated averages. In spatially uniform systems, the last term in equation (A1) is zero [20, 21]. In [9, 10], there is a mistake, where the \bar{s}_i in equation (A1) are assumed to be the averages when the interaction between spins is present, and thus the derivation of equation (9) of this study given there is incorrect. The magnetisation of a system is the average of the magnetic moment per site [10], i.e.:

$$\sigma = \langle s_i \rangle = \frac{\langle s_1 + s_2 + \dots + s_N \rangle}{N}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

Since the system is translation invariant, it follows that $\langle s_i \rangle = \langle s_{i+1} \rangle$ and

$$\sigma^2 = \langle s_i \rangle^2 = \langle s_i \rangle \langle s_{i+1} \rangle. \quad (\text{A3})$$

We can write that

$$\langle s_i \rangle^2 = \frac{(s_1 + s_2 + \cdots + s_N)^2}{N^2} = \langle s_i \rangle \langle s_{i+1} \rangle. \quad (\text{A4})$$

For large N , this equation can be rewritten in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle s_i \rangle^2 &= \frac{s_1(s_1 + s_2 + \cdots + s_N) + s_2(s_1 + s_2 + \cdots + s_N) + \cdots}{N^2} \\ &= \frac{s_1 \langle s_2 \rangle + s_2 \langle s_3 \rangle + \cdots + s_{N-1} \langle s_N \rangle + s_1^2}{N}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

It can be rewritten like this:

$$\langle s_i \rangle^2 = \frac{\langle s_1 s_2 \rangle + \langle s_2 s_3 \rangle + \cdots + \langle s_{N-1} s_N \rangle}{N} + \frac{s_1^2}{N}. \quad (\text{A6})$$

At large N , equation (A6) turns into:

$$\langle s_i \rangle^2 = \langle s_i s_{i+1} \rangle. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Therefore, from equations (A1), (A3) and (A7), it follows that:

$$\sigma^2 = \langle s_i s_{i+1} \rangle = \Gamma(1), \quad (\text{A8})$$

i.e., equation (10) is proven for large N . The consequence that follows from this result is that the long-range order equals the short-range order, namely:

$$\langle s_i s_{i+1} \rangle = \langle s_i s_k \rangle = \Gamma(1) = \Gamma(2) = \cdots, \quad (\text{A9})$$

where $k > i + 1$.

Let us check equation (A8) practically. We can model an Ising chain with a random number generator. If N_- is the number of spins down, then the magnetisation of the chain is:

$$\sigma = \frac{N - 2N_-}{N}. \quad (\text{A10})$$

The nearest-neighbour correlation function can be calculated like that:

$$\Gamma(1) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} s_i s_{i+1}}{N-1}. \quad (\text{A11})$$

In Table 1, the results of a simulation of an Ising chain with $N = 1000$ are given. Equation (A8) agrees very well with the reality for $\sigma > 0.3$, but not well for lower σ . However, for $N = 10,000$ and $N_- = 4000, 4500$ and 5000 , σ from equation (A8) is equal to 0.2, 0.13 and 0.1, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison of the magnetisation of an Ising chain with 1000 spins obtained from equation (A10) and from numerical experiment, equation (A8)

N_-	σ , eq. (A10)	$\Gamma(1)$, eq. (A11)	σ , eq. (A8)	N_-	σ , eq. (A10)	$\Gamma(1)$, eq. (A11)	σ , eq. (A8)
50	0.9	0.81	0.90	300	0.4	0.16	0.40
100	0.8	0.62	0.79	350	0.3	0.13	0.35
150	0.7	0.48	0.69	400	0.2	0.12	0.34
200	0.6	0.36	0.60	450	0.1	0.09	0.30
250	0.5	0.25	0.50	500	0	0.04	0.21